

SOME ISSUES FROM THE HISTORY OF THE ART OF MAQOM. THE USE
OF THE MAQOM DIDACTIC MATERIALS IN THE TEACHING AND
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Abstract: *The work describes issues of the history of the Uzbek maqom folklore genre. Based on scientific sources, theoretical and methodological conclusions are drawn in the work.*

Keywords: *maqom, art, Uzbek folklore, genre, Shashmaqom, UNESCO, World Heritage List.*

One of the five most important action strategy on the priority development areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan, developed personally by President Mirziyoyev for 2017-2021, refers to the development of the social sphere in the republic. The leadership of our republic and the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan are conducting extensive and fruitful work on the spiritual renewal of society, the revival of ancient national traditions, culture and art as well. [1]

The study of Uzbek folklore genres, and particularly the art of maqoms, in the process of teaching humanities, students form an understanding of the genetic link between language and literature and folklore, and of the role of genres in the genesis and formation of literary genres, and of the use of traditions, artistic mastery of reality, developed over thousands of years in oral-poetic art, in the literary process.

Uzbek maqom art, like other genres of folklore, developed on the basis of oral and written art.

Shashmaqom, one of the principal genres of classical music in Central Asia, is represented in the musical culture of the Uzbek and Tajik peoples. Shashmak is a refined instrumental music and a highly professional vocal art. [2]

The homeland of "Shashmaqom" is Bukhara. The art of music developed in Maverannahr in the 9th and early 13th centuries. Most scholars of maqoms believe that tunes such as "Boda", "Ushshok", "Rost", "Khusrawoni" and "Zerafkanda" were sung in the early Middle Ages. All these tunes later formed the basis of the classic melody Shashmaqom [3]. According to authoritative researchers of maqom art, Bukhara's Shashmaqom appeared at the end of the 18th century. [4]

President Mirziyoyev said: "The Shashmaqom, a collection of six maqoms, is the fruit of the musical genius of our people - like six full-flowing rivers.

of our people - like six full-flowing rivers. It flows in the ocean of world culture, supplementing and enriching it. It is deeply symbolic that this unique cultural phenomenon has been recognized by the UNESCO World Heritage List.

unique cultural phenomenon has been recognized by UNESCO as a masterpiece of the intangible cultural heritage of humanity'. The immense respect and full support of our esteemed President for the art of maqom was evident when the National Maqom Art Centre was established in 2017 as per a presidential decree. Remarkably, in 2018, the city of Shahrissabz hosted the International Maqom Art Festival was held in the city of Shahrissabz in 2018. [6]

The history of Maqom art is closely intertwined with the political history of

The history of Maqom art is closely intertwined with the political history of Central Asia. The history of Maqom art is closely intertwined with the political history of Central Asian countries. It is known that an eminent political and statesman, a great connoisseur and connoisseur of Maqom art, was a master of the Maqom art. Muhammad Rakhimkhan Soni (Feruz), a great connoisseur and master of maqoms, was the most prominent political figure of the Central Asian countries.

Rahimhan 2 Soni (Feruz) issued a special decree in 1882, which said the decree read in part: "I, the Supreme Ruler of the State of Khorezm, Muhammad Rahimkhan Soni, signing this decree that "Khorezmian maqoms should be recognized as the inviolable property of the people to establish extreme penalties for those who dare to express doubts on the present decree, diminish the dignity and significance or perform them in a distorted manner". [7] The art of maqom was directly related to the daily.

It was designed to facilitate the difficult process of labor, to inspire and to give a peculiar life-affirming impulse in the process of labor. According to the unknown. According to an unknown author of the musical manual "Risolai musikiy" ("Book about Music"), maqom songs are composed on the basis of 12 months, which is a yearly cycle. For example, "Rost" is the Muslim month of Hamal (March), "Isfahoni" is Savr (April), "Irok" is Javzo (the month of May). "Zarafkanda"-sarathon (month of June).The tune "Buzruk"-asad (month of July respectively). Melody "Rost"-sunbula (month of August, respectively), etc.[8].

Alisher Navoi, the founder of Uzbek literature and a genius of poetry, in his book "Seven planets" expressed his admiration for the art of maqom.

[9] In his "Turt arba'ulus" "The history of the four peoples", the eminent statesman Mirzo Ulugbek describes the folk melodies of the four peoples.

Four Nations' gives a description of folk tunes of Maqom.[10] These facts show that well-known historical figures were very well aware of the educational

were well aware of the educational and aesthetic role of Maqom art and its important and enduring significance in the spiritual and cultural development of the younger generation.

At present, scientific methodological literature identifies

the following types of interaction between arts, namely literature and music are identified in the scientific methodological literature: inter-subject links within the traditional curriculum, and an integrated approach to poly-art education of students.

Teaching individual arts on a multi-artistic basis and combining compulsory subjects of the aesthetic cycle with extra-curricular activities. This approach can be implemented through concerts, literary and musical compositions. In doing this the concert is at the same time a means of enabling direct contact between the students and true masterpieces of maqom art.

In the context of linking interdisciplinary disciplines in the teaching of literature, the description of works in which the main characters are singers, whether the ancient Greek

legendary Orpheus or outstanding singers of Turkestan folk songs - Tuychi Hofiz, Ata Jalal, Barno Iskhakova, Mirsadyk Tadzhiyev,

Berta Davydova, Saodat Kabulova, Kommuna Ismailova, Munajat Yulchieva Hero of Uzbekistan and others. They had a masterly way of controlling their audiences, imbuing them with inner peace and making them

empathise with every line of a maqom song. This is especially well described in the story "The Singers" by the great Russian writer Ivan Sergeevich Turgenev.

Turgenev's The Singers. The story The Singers describes the creative state of two talented singers in Oryol province - a rower from

from a place called Jizdra and Yashka the Turk. Here is how the writer describes the performance of Yashka-Turka: "He sang, and from every sound of his voice reeked of something native and immensely wide, as if a familiar steppe opened up before you, reaching into the infinite distance. I felt my heart boil and tears rise to my eyes: muffled, subdued sobs suddenly startled me" [11].

While studying the work of Russian poets, the so-called "Silver Age", it is advisable to draw historical and musical

parallels in the song art of the Russian Empire and the Turkestan region, late 19th and early 20th centuries. The works of the great Russian tenor Feodor Chaliapin and original singer of Turkestan region Tuychi-Hafiz Tashmukhammedov are of great interest for the students. Noteworthy

In 1905 the Riga firm "Gramophone" recorded his song "Hisrav", and he sang more than 25 folk songs such as "Bobo Ravshan", "Yo khayotan nabi", "Bevafo dunyosan", "Suvora", "Ilgor" and others [12].

The art of maqom contributes to the formation of many positive qualities in pupils. The ideological and moral content of folk songs and melodies of maqoms can unite them in a common happy aesthetic experience. Uzbek maqoms are one of the most effective means of educating the new generation; they have great emotional power and nurture feelings and form high aesthetic tastes.

The art of maqoms is unique in its musical, poetic, aesthetic and pedagogical form. The beauty and goodness of maqom tunes are in unity. Their main purpose is to instill love for beauty and to develop aesthetic attitudes and tastes in students.

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